

The Impact of Students' Attitude Towards English Language on Academic Achievement

Clark R. Colaste

Secondary School Teacher I

Felisberto Verano National High School, Tandag, Philippines

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of students' attitude towards English language on academic achievement. This study used Universal sampling because it considered the two classes of the grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School. One class is composed of 43 learners and the other class comprised of 45 students a total of Eighty eight (88) students as the chosen respondents of this study.

The descriptive quantitative method of research was used to determine the impact of English language anxiety on the students' academic achievement. A Likert-scale was used to measure the anxiety level of English language classroom activity and the attitude of grade 9 students toward English; the scale was rated using the following options: Strongly Disagree-1, Disagree-2, Undecided-3, Agree-4, Strongly Agree-5, 1-Very Relaxed, 2-Moderately Relaxed, 3-Anxious, 4-Moderately Anxious, 5-Very Anxious.

The statistical tools used in analyzing the data of this study were weighted mean and Pearson Product Moment of Correlation (Pearson-r). The weighted mean was used to determine the attitude and anxiety of grade 9 students towards English language classroom activities using the MPS of the respondents for the second grading of AY 2017-2018 as data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson-r) was used to determine the significant relationships between the respondents' MPS and Attitude towards English Language, MPS and Level of Anxiety towards English Class Activities, and the significant relationship between attitude and the level of anxiety.

The findings revealed that the grade 9 students who participated in this study generally have the negative attitude towards English as a subject. They revealed

that they dislike English as a subject because they find it difficult to express themselves using language as a medium of communication. Moreover, on the statement "I have heard of the phrase Filipino-English" got the lowest in rank which means they were unaware or they do not have an idea of a Filipino-English phrase.

As to their level of anxiety, it was revealed that most of the students have difficulty when the teacher gives a speaking activity requiring mental adeptness such as debate. Moreover, they also display hesitation when speaking before a crowd because of their fear of being corrected in front of everybody.

On the significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and the attitude towards English, the way that students think and behave towards English language whether positive or negative is highly correlated to their academic performance. On the significant relationship between respondents MPS and level of anxiety, it failed to reject the null hypothesis; therefore there is no significant relationship between anxiety level on their academic performance. Having failed to reject the null hypotheses on the significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and level of anxiety and between the students' attitude and level of anxiety, it can be further inferred that there are no significant relationships between the tested variables.

Based on the findings of the study, there is a need to come up with speaking strategies to provide an avenue where students can be most apprehensive. However, because the macro skills are complementary, other skills also need to be addressed.

Keywords: *Attitude, Language Anxiety*

INTRODUCTION:

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

Learning English as a second language is a long and challenging process for learners. Students' success and academic achievement in learning this new language depend on many internal and external factors. The quality of language education, teacher, and curriculum can be considered as some of the external factors in language learning. Internal factors such as attitude, anxiety and self-confidence exert a distinctive influence on students' individual success at their English language courses; therefore, it is important to reveal these internal factors (Zefran, 2015). This study claims that students face factors that impede performance in the classroom. These experiences are oftentimes contributing to their anxiety in the class.

Attitude is characterized by a large proportion of emotional involvement such as feelings, self, and relationships in the community. Learning could not come about easily unless students have positive attitudes toward it on one hand, and attitudes might originate from life experiences, on the other hand. As such, since attitude can influence success or failure in learning it plays a very crucial role. Ajzen (2005) believes that like any personality trait, attitude is a directly unobserved hypothetical construct and must be inferred from measurable responses which reflect and evaluate positive or negative attitudes as cited by Dehbozorgi (2012).

Ohat (2005) cites that English Language anxiety is a type of anxiety specifically associated with learning the second language (L2), and it can arise from many kinds of sources. In the locale, students display apprehension when asked to participate orally in class as observed by most teachers most especially when the medium of instruction used is English. In consonance, research shows that language anxiety impedes successful language learning among second and foreign language learners, In the study conducted by Lucas, & Miraflores (2011), it was found out that learners are challenged with many situational factors, anxiety may arise and as a result, their performance is hampered.

This study endeavors to address the issues on students' attitude and anxiety faced by the junior high school students when using English as a medium of

expression in class interaction. Hence activities to diminish, if not eradicate, anxiety will be proposed to make the teaching and learning process meaningful and productive especially in learning the English language.

Theoretical/ Conceptual framework

This study claims that situational factors result to anxiety which in turn affects classroom performance. This study is anchored on Krashen's Affective filter theory which provides that language anxiety affects students' performance. The theory puts emphasis on the idea that it was anxiety which inhabited that learners' ability to process incoming language and impeding the processing of acquisition. Thus, if anxiety impaired the cognitive, students who were anxious learned less and were not able to demonstrate what they learned. Therefore, they experienced even more failure, which in turn escalated anxiety (Hipster, 2009).

In the Affective Filter hypothesis, Krashen as cited by Schutz (2007), explained motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety all affect language acquisition, in effect raising or lowering the stickiness or penetration of any comprehensible input that is received. In addition, Krogh (2011) laid down that one of the five key hypothesis of second language acquisition that Krashen discusses is the "Affective Filter Theory." In this hypothesis, Krashen shows that motivation, self-confidence, and anxiety all play a prominent role in language acquisition. These factors become crucial in the process of language acquisition, either heightening or inferring with a student's ability to progress.

Krashen articulates that students who are highly motivated, have a strong sense of self, and enter a learning situation with low level of anxiety are much likely to be successful language acquirers than those who do not.

Furthermore, when the affective filter blocks comprehensible input, acquisition fails or occurs to a lesser extent than when affective filter supports the intake of comprehensible input. The affective filter, therefore, accounts for individual's variation in second language acquisition. Second language instruction can and should work to minimize the effects of the affective filter.

In addition, this study is supported by Horwitz and his colleagues (1986) who articulated that language

anxiety as distinct complex of self-perceptions, beliefs, feelings, and behaviors related to classroom learning arising from the uniqueness of the language learning process. They also found that foreign language anxiety can be related to the following: a) communication apprehension (the fear of communicating with other people), b) test anxiety (fear of exams, quizzes, and other activities used to evaluate one's competence), and c) fear of negative evaluation (worry about how others view the speaker).

Communication apprehension is characterized by fear and anxiety in communicating with people. Difficulty in speaking in public, listening or learning a spoken utterance are all manifestations of communication apprehension. This type of anxiety in learning a second language is derived from the learners' personal knowledge that they will have difficulty understanding others and making themselves understood.

Test anxiety is a type of performance anxiety which is caused by fear of failing a test. Test anxious students often put unrealistic demands on themselves; it is considered to be one of the most important aspects of negative motivation which will affect learning. This type of fear is defined as an unpleasant feeling or emotional state that has both physiological and behavioral concomitants and that is experienced an anxious learner when taking formal test or other evaluative situations.

Furthermore, test anxiety has been defined as the reaction to stimuli that are associated with an individual's experience of testing or evaluating situations. Stober (2004) mentioned that there are two main components of test anxiety: worry and emotional status. Worry refers to concerns about being evaluated and the results of exam failure; and secondly, emotion refers to the perceptions and reactions evoked by the test situation. In general, test anxiety includes a number of different symptoms such

as inability to pay attention and concentrate, awareness of bodily sensations and tension, and so on, leads to academic failure in the long run (Sena, Lowe, and Lee, 2007). There is no denying that one of the factors related to low academic performance and achievement is test anxiety, and some studies mentioned that test anxiety is highly prevalent among students. For example, a research finding revealed that there is a significant difference of academic achievement among three levels of test anxiety. Students with low test anxiety had higher academic achievement than students with moderate and higher test anxiety. Similarly, students with moderate test anxiety had higher academic achievement than students with higher test anxiety (Chapell, Blanding, and Silverstein, 2005). Aside from that, Sansigiry and Sail (2006) noted that test anxiety causes irrelevant thoughts, decreased attention and concentration, thus leads to academic failure. Also, it is linked to memory and has a negative impact on academic performance.

Fear of negative evaluation is the apprehension about other people's evaluations. This may also include avoidance of evaluative situations and the expectations that others might evaluate them negatively. It may also include the student's fear inside the English classroom where factors such as learning activities, teacher's methodology and even peer pressure may contribute to novice language learners' anxieties.

As shown in figure 1. The first box below represents the dependent variables which include the attitude towards English language and the level of anxiety towards the use of English in class. The second box indicates the MPS of the grade 9 learners in the second grading period. This indicator is included to evaluate whether anxiety has affected how these students academically performed. The speaking strategies will be the output of the study, as shown in the third box.

Figure1. Schematic Diagram of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to know the English language anxiety among Grade-9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School students of Cortes I District.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the attitude of Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School towards English Language class activities?
2. What is the level of English Language Anxiety prevalent among Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School?
3. What is the MPS of Grade-9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School Students in the second grading?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and their attitude towards English class activities?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and their level of anxiety towards the English language class?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School and their level of anxiety towards English Language based on the findings and the study?
7. What strategies can be suggested to improve the academic achievement of the Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School?

Hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and their attitude towards English language class activities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the MPS and level of anxiety towards the English language class.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents towards the English language class interaction and their level of anxiety.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on the students' attitude towards English language on academic achievement among FVNHS Grade-9 students of Cortes I District, Poblacion, Cortes, Surigao del Sur.

The respondents of the study included the junior high school students of Felisberto Verano National High

School of Cortes I District. There were 88 respondents of this study who supplied data on questionnaire during the AY 2017-2018.

This topic is relevant to the issues currently existing in today's generation, specifically to foster the English students of FVNHS.

Significance of the Study

This study may have some implications on English Language teaching as a solution to the problem of access and the quest towards quality education. A research therefore relative to its implication and or its outcomes is very significant to various groups.

Administrators The result of the study will give administrators to have Technical Assistance to the teachers who are in need and probably provide what they needs. It will also give awareness to those concerned in the governing of the institution of how they can propose and facilitate indoor progress that can be used by the teachers in inviting meaningful and engaging interest of the students in the class discussion.

Teachers This is a big help for the teachers in choosing strategies and activities in teaching English subjects that is engaging and remembering so that students would participate.

Future researchers The study is profitable for the future researchers that they would be guided and inspired to develop another related study and explore the limitless scope of other authentic strategies for new and anticipated pedagogies of English and would not be stuck in an orthodox way of teaching English subjects.

Definition of Terms

To provide a clear understanding, the following terms are operationally defined in this study:

Academic Achievement As used in the study, it refers to the level of learning in a particular area subject in terms of knowledge, understanding, skill and application usually evaluated by teachers in the form of test scores and performance tasks in their annual examination.

Anxiety As used in the study, this refers to the positive or negative feelings manifested by the students towards English language.

Attitudes As used in the study, it is the students' positive and negative attitude towards English language.

Language Anxiety As used in the study, this is the feeling of apprehension developed by the students when they are asked to do certain activities in their English class; it develops in them a fear of participation that comes from certain reasons such as fear of committing mistakes, being corrected before a crowd, and etc.

MPS As used in the study, it is the total weighted mean in every grading period. It indicates the ratio between the number of correctly answered items in a test and the total number of items.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This section contains the review of related literature and studies in the country and abroad which have direct bearing with the present study.

Related Literatures

Foreign

In his great work Principles of Language Learning and Teaching, Brown (1994) as cited by Eshghinejad (2016) discussed that attitude concept can be viewed from three dimensions regarding aspects of it. Each one of these dimensions has different features to bring out language attitude results, behavioral, cognitive, and affective. These three attitudinal aspects are based on the three theoretical approaches of behaviorism, cognitivism, and humanism, respectively.

The behavioral aspect of attitude (BAA) deals with the way one behaves and reacts in particular situations. Kara (2009) stated that positive attitude leads to the exhibition of positive behavior toward studying, absorbing themselves in it, and striving to learn more. Such students are also observed to show more enthusiasm to solve problems, to acquire what is useful for daily life, and to engage themselves emotionally.

Cognitive aspect of attitude (CAA) involves the beliefs of the language learners about the knowledge that they receive and their understanding of the process of language learning. The cognitive attitude could be classified into four steps of connecting the previous knowledge and the new one, creating new knowledge, checking new knowledge, and applying

the new knowledge in many situations (Eshghinejad, 2016).

With respect to the emotional attitude, Feng and Chen (2009) stated that learning process is an emotional process; it is affected by different emotional factors. The teacher and his students engage in various emotional activities in it and varied results of emotions are yield.

Different people have defined differently the concept of attitude. To begin with, Anold (2005) as cited by Nyamubi (2016) defines attitude as either mental readiness or implicit predispositions that exert some general or consistent influence on a fairly large class of evaluative responses, which are usually directed towards some objects, events or persons. On the other hand, Ewen (2003) as cited by Nyamubi (2016) defines attitude as a mental and neural state of readiness organised through experience, exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related.

The common characteristic in these definitions is that attitudes entail evaluative predispositions to respond to social objects that interact with situational variables, thus guiding and directing the overt behaviour of an individual. The working definitions preferred in this study are Ajzen's (2001) as cited by Nyamubi (2016), who defines attitude as a disposition to respond favourably or unfavourably to an object, person or event, and Armitage and Conner's (2001), who see that the role of attitudes is to help locate objects of thought, such as language, as being an object that is perceived to be favourable or unfavourable. These definitions are preferred because they link attitudes to measurement, that is, whether they are favourable or unfavourable in relation to an object, person or event.

In this way, if an attitude of a person to an object such as language is known, it can be used in conjunction with situations and it can explain a person's reaction to it. A survey of attitudes provides an indicator of current community thoughts, beliefs, preferences and desires (Garrett, 2010). Attitudes are feelings of approval and disapproval to learn a language; it is comprised of beliefs about things that have some social significance. Such beliefs, for example, can be values that are attached to English by many Tanzanians that knowing the language is synonymous

to being educated (Mapunda, 2013). It also provides social indicators of changing beliefs and the chance of success in language policy implementation.

In education, attitudes could be both an input and an output. A favourable attitude to language learning may be a vital input in language achievement. Baker (1992) as cited by Nyamubi (2016) found the following: first, attitudes have a positive correlation with success in learning a second language; and second, they facilitate learners' motivation to learn the language in relation to goal attainment. Attitudes can also be an outcome. After a language-learning course, the teacher and learners may have favourable attitudes to the language learnt, if they expect to benefit from it. In this way, learners will strive to achieve highly in the expectation of doing well in examinations and mastering the language, which in turn facilitates better performance.

Gardner (1985) In Nyamubi (2016) argued that second language learners with positive attitudes towards the target language learn more effectively than those who do not have such positive attitudes. He explains that learners' language attitudes predict students' degree of success in terms of linguistic outcomes in learning the target language.

In language learning, attitudes seem to be very important in predicting learners' academic performance. The learner's favourable attitude to the language she/he is learning would facilitate success in it. Tahaine and Daana (2013) argue that personal beliefs about one's capabilities and positive attitudes towards what one is learning positively influence learning. In this way, learners' positive attitudes to the language they are learning could help them to master the language, leading to success in their performance at school and after school linguistic needs in real daily-life situations.

English language anxiety has become a great concern in a second language research over the last three decades according to Trang (2012) due to the specific nature of foreign language and the amount of fear and apprehension relate to learning such languages.

English language anxiety has become a great concern in foreign and second language research over the last three decades (Trang, 2012). In general, academic anxiety can be defined as a unifying formulation for the collection of anxieties learners experience while in

schools (Cassady, 2010). MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) as cited by Subaşı (2010) defined language anxiety as the feeling of tension and apprehension specifically associated with second language texts, including speaking, listening, and learning.

Learning an English language is challenging since it requires much time and effort, and is not always an easy and pleasant activity even for a language enthusiast (Lam, 2009). The problem of anxiety is one of the affective factors that exist among Yemeni EFL students even those who have gained an advanced level of proficiency (Ezzi, 2012). Students experience anxiety not only inside the classroom but also outside the classroom especially when they use the language in real communicative situations (Tanveer, 2007).

Anxiety is defined by Horwitz (1986) in Nefti (2013) is perceived intuitively by many language learners, negatively influences language learning and has been found to be one of the most highly examined variables in all psychology and education. Also he defined anxiety as a a feeling of tension, apprehension and nervousness associated with the situation of learning a foreign language. A similar definition was provided by Scovel in Algeria (2015) who argued that anxiety in learning is an emotional state of apprehension, a vague fear that is only indirectly associated with an object. English language anxiety is a form of what psychologists as Stephen Krashen described as specific anxiety reaction. Some individuals are more predisposed to anxiety than others, may feel anxious in a wide variety of situations. English language anxiety, however it is a specific situation and so can also affect individuals who are not characteristically anxious in other situations.

Sarason and his associates in Legesse (2014) believed that anxiety had its roots in early childhood with both developmental and environmental elements. They proposed that these elements are all linked to perceived feelings of insecurity and inadequacy that are carried into adulthood. The feeling of anxiety is very common. Some people refer to it as nervous and everyone with varied situations, has experienced anxiety at one time or another. The feeling of general uneasiness, a sense of foreboding and a feeling of tension is something that happens in our day to-day lives. Anxiety has both a physiological and a psychological aspect and it is the psychological aspect that affects the way we interpret sensations (Clark and Beck, 2011).

According to Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) in Nefti (2013), there is a unique type of anxiety that is specific to foreign language which is originated from a situation-specific anxiety. Chen and Chang (2004) found that academic learning history as well as test characteristics was not predictive variables of foreign language anxiety.

Tobias as cited by Legesse (2014) described anxiety as an affective state. Since most learning was a cognitively mediated process, anxiety affected learning only indirectly by impacting on cognitive processes at various stages. The author continued to describe learning in terms of the three classical information processing components: input, processing, and output. Input involves the presentation of instructional material to students. Processing encompasses the operations used to register, record, organize, store, and retrieve instructional input. Output denoted the measurement of achievement of the instructional objective. He took these components and developed a model that described the effects of anxiety on learning from instruction. According to this model, anxiety potentially influenced the learning at three possible points: pre-processing, during and after processing, and prior to output.

Anxiety influences students in learning language because it can totally prevent students from achieving their goals in learning due to they are all time fearful, and do not feel protected from classroom environment. Thus, their anxiety has strong effect on their achievements (Wrench, et al., 2009). Paying attention to this factor of learning should also be taken into consideration. Among other effective variables, anxiety stands out as one of the main blocking factor for effective language learning (Nascente, 2001).

Kleinman (2009) divided anxiety into two kinds: 1) facilitating, 2) debilitating anxiety, with the first is valuable to performance and with the second is harmful to performance. English language anxiety itself can have opposite views about the effect of it on language learning where debilitating anxiety presents an obstruction to learning, whereas facilitating anxiety fosters and assist the progress of it.

Anxiety has already appeared in many aspects in language teaching for decades according to Negari & Rezaabadi (2012). All of English basic skills such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening have been the

media where anxiety can develop to affect the students' psychology in achieving a successful learning. As Negari & Rezaabadi (2012) pointed out that even though little amount of anxiety is needed by EFL students to be more careful on the usage of English, but too much apprehension will affect the students' performance negatively and drive them to big problems. In addition, Wu (2010) said it is true that anxiety is a major challenge for EFL students so that they need to find a way to overcome that feeling of apprehension. That is why there are many studies which have such an interest on investigating the anxiety to many aspects of students' learning as well as several strategies in order the students' can figure out the tension that is caused by anxiety.

Sharkawi (2009) defined language anxiety as the: apprehension experienced when a situation requires the use of a second language with which the individual is not fully proficient. It is, therefore, seen as a stable personality trait referring to the propensity for an individual to react in a nervous manner when speaking, listening, reading, or writing in the second language.

Moreover, fear of negative evaluation is essentially a cognitive construct and may be particularly amenable to cognitive interventions (Anderson & Hope, 2014). In an EFL context, it refers to academic evaluation as well as personal evaluations of the learners on the basis of their performance (Toth, 2010). Finally, the last component of foreign language anxiety is test apprehension or test anxiety. Test anxiety is an apprehension over academic evaluation. It is a fear of failing in tests and an unpleasant experience held consciously or unconsciously by learners. It is the fear of exams, quizzes, and other assignments used to evaluate students' performance (Wu, 2010).

Wörde (2008) posted that the questions on the factors that contribute to anxiety, is the students belief on anxiety as hindrance to language acquisition, the factors that the students believe to reduce anxiety, ways that anxiety manifest on the participants and the language that triggers the most anxiety. The reason for this is anxiety as a lexicon was often interchanged with the words nervousness and frustration. However, most of the participants feel better knowing that others also experience the same way.

Worde (2008) cited several factors that contribute to students anxiety such as participating in speaking

activities, inability to understand the lessons, and evaluation among others. Peer affiliation or a feeling communal connectedness, classroom set-up and teacher's role were referred to by the participants as factors that reduce anxiety. His research as a whole is thorough and suggestive since it encompassed language learning anxiety in both mental and physical condition of the participants. It appears that the students were more receptive in answering the face to face interview questions probably because relating and or recalling negative instances relieves them of the pain associated to it.

In an article entitled English language learning anxiety among Iranian EFL freshmen university learners Yamat and Bidabadi (2012) claimed that while the freshmen experienced more anxiety on being negatively evaluated they found no significant difference in foreign language learning anxiety regarding gender; nonetheless, the participants were anxious and nervous in terms of language skills. However, they stated that males were more anxious in case of communication and tests whereas females showed more anxiety in English classes and fear of being negatively evaluated.

Local

Facing up your fear is said to be the better way rather than escaping it. This ideology is something that influenced yourself to conquer anxieties in speaking and writing in the English language.

In the Philippines, the utilization of English as a second language has come into point that every a Filipino is yet fond patronizing much of knowing its benefits towards them are greatly encouraging and worth spending effort for. But learning it is quite hard especially when there is extremely no interest to merely urge ourselves to be diligent and patient upon attaining the highest level of learning-comprehension as well as using the language pertinent to the grammar rules. Grammar is vehemently prioritized than understanding in teaching Filipinos to speak in English, particularly when studying at school. So, either of the two macro skills, speaking and writing, use the language grammatically correct because if not someone will definitely notice it though there is fluency of language usage (Saysi, 2012).

Related Studies

Foreign

Yang (2012) in Ahmeed (2015) found out that learners who were highly and positively involved in

their English proficiency had positive attitudes and were highly motivated towards learning English.

Fakeye (2010) in Eshghinejad (2016) determined that there is a significant relationship between attitude and achievement was the result found in that study. Additionally, it was explored that students' attitude is not gender-related. Thus, there was not a statistically significant difference in the attitudes of male and female students.

Fisher, et al. (2013) indicated that girls during adolescence are more motivated to learn compared with their peer boys, which is also reflected in results of their learning. Candeias, Rebelo & Oliveira (2010) note that girls seem to have more positive attitudes toward school, while boys are less motivated and have more negative attitudes toward school.

Latifah, et al. (2011) in Ahmeed (2015) discovered that personal motivation plays an insignificant impact, attitude plays a positive impact on performance in the English course conducted at Open University Malaysia.

Abidin, et al. (2012) in Eshghinejad (2016) found out that their participants have a negative attitude in all three aspects of behavioral, cognitive, and emotional toward learning English.

Mamun, et al. (2012) in Ahmeed (2015) determined that the learners have positive attitudes towards English language and their motivational orientation were instrumental in nature.

Kubiatko (2013) argued that if attitudes towards a subject and school are positive, also the achievement of students gets better. The achievement of a student could be defined as individual progress, improvement in terms of acquired knowledge, skills and competences. Many teachers, as is apparent from the study of Holúbková & Glasová (2011) associated academic achievement with a positive attitude of a student towards school that may not be necessarily reflected in excellent achievements, although it will be reflected in producing the best individual performance in relation to a student's dispositions. Academic achievement should be also analysed in a relation to a student's attitude towards learning and school, as it ensures internal motivation for providing better performance.

Chalak & Kassaian (2010) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) learned that these EFL learners tend to learn English for both instrumental and integrative reasons and their attitude towards the target language is generally highly positive in nature.

Momani (2009) as cited by Abidin (2012) investigated the secondary stage students' attitudes towards learning English as a foreign language and their achievements in reading comprehension. The findings showed that the respondents had neutral positive attitudes toward learning English. Also, there was a strong correlation between the students' attitudes toward learning English and their performance in reading comprehension.

Galloway (2011) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) suggested that the learners deem English belonging to the native English speakers and they want to learn native English. The results highlighted that a number of factors influence students' attitude.

Bobkina & Fernandez (2012) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) determined that the predominant motivation among Spanish engineering students is extrinsic in nature and most of the students have positive attitude towards the social values and educational status of English. Moreover, students' have positive orientation towards the English language.

Tahaineh & Daana (2013) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) informed that the learners' motivation was instrumental in nature having utilitarian and academic reasons with the least impact of culture in it, whereas their attitude towards learning the target language and its community was highly positive.

Goktepe (2014) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) discovered that these learners learn English mostly for instrumental reasons and also integrative motivation is dominant motivational orientation for the learners in some degree.

Samadani & Ibnian (2015) as cited by Ahmeed (2015) revealed that the learners have overall positive attitude towards English and that students with high GPA have the highest positive attitude towards English, followed by the medium and the low GPA students.

Shams (2008) as cited by Eshghinejad, (2016) found that the students had affirmative attitudes and high

enthusiasm toward English. This also highlighted that most of them showed positive attitudes toward English language and its learning which, in turn, emphasized the value of English language efficiency in the daily life.

Al-Tamimi and Shuib (2009) as cited by Abidin (2012) revealed that they had positive attitudes towards the use of English in the Yemeni social and educational contexts. They also showed affirmative attitude towards the culture of the English speaking world.

Al-Zahrani (2008) as cited by Abidin (2012) found out that there was not any clear difference among the three years in their attitudes towards Learning English as the descriptive statistics showed that the respondents in the three years had the same level of attitude.

Sejčová (2006) as cited by Veresova & Mala (2016) determined an important factor contributing to good results of students in individual subjects is their attitude towards them. He indicated that an attitude towards a subject reflects a measure of popularity that, in turn, reflects a tendency to undertake actions required by the subject and the satisfaction gained from these actions.

Kara (2009) as cited by Eshghinejad (2016) stated that positive attitude leads to the exhibition of positive behavior toward studying, absorbing themselves in it, and striving to learn more. Such students are also observed to show more enthusiasm to solve problems, to acquire what is useful for daily life, and to engage themselves emotionally.

Wang (2006) as cited by kaur & Singh (2014) mentioned that learning a language is a very complex process and involves internal and external reasons. Learners will show a positive attitude if they want to learn the language and negative attitude if they do not want to learn the language. However, positive attitude always strengthens the motivation. There are also situations where one shows a neutral feeling towards second language learning when they have no choice but to learn the language in order to complete their school's requirement. Pan, Zang and Wu (2010) explain that if the learner wants to learn a language, it will have to show a positive attitude.

Nancy (2003) as cited by kaur & Singh (2014) determined that the students were very interested and motivated to learn the subject in English and positive attitude was shown. They also felt that learning Mathematics in English was a challenging task, but they still enjoyed learning it. In this study it was seen that the students who are not proficient in English were the ones lacked confidence and were feeling uncomfortable.

Liu (2007) as cited by kaur & Singh (2014) found a lot of positive attitude towards English language learning and this resulted in high scores in their proficiency test. The conclusion that can be gathered from this study is that if the respondents show positive attitude, the results will be excellent.

Singh & Thukral (2009) reported an inverse relationship between academic achievement and academic anxiety. Singh (2009) found a significant negative correlation between academic achievement and academic anxiety.

Vogel and Collins cited by Legesse (2014) found that students with high-test anxiety as well as those students with low-test anxiety showed lower academic performance. Moreover, those students with moderate levels of test anxiety performed well.

Another study was conducted by Tiegist (2010) noted that socially anxious groups had lower GPA as compared to that of the non-socially anxious participants. It is possible to say that the lower GPA of socially anxious groups was due to their socially anxiety.

Yamat and Bidabadi (2012) revealed that these university students experienced the anxiety of being evaluated negatively in EFL classrooms. The findings also demonstrated no statistically significant difference between male and female EFL learners.

Izadi and Atasheneh (2012) investigated the effects of FLL anxiety on the communicative skills of listening and speaking of a sample of 30 Iranian EFL students. They found that anxiety is a matter which is directly related to the students' self-confidence and self-esteem.

Shabani (2012) determined that participants suffered from language anxiety and fear of negative evaluation. The findings demonstrated that the prime

sources of language anxiety and fear of negative evaluation are fear of failing the class and fear of leaving unfavorable impression on others, respectively.

Mahmoodzadeh (2012) concluded that the female participants were found to be more prone to experiencing EFL speaking anxiety.

In a follow-up study, Mahmoodzadeh (2013) found out, highlighting language classroom anxiety, indicated that mixed-gender classrooms can be considered as an anxiety-provoking teaching context in Iran, since the presence of the opposite gender in EFL classrooms was found to cause statistically significant amount of language anxiety among Iranian learners.

Nahavandi and Mukundan (2013) explored the level of anxiety of 548 Iranian students the results of the study indicated that communication anxiety was the predominant anxiety component among English-major students.

Al-Seraj (2011) found out that anxiety-provoking situations included the environment, the teacher, and the content of material in the class, as well as the communication style.

Rezazadeh and Tavakoli (2009), Riasati (2011), AzarfamandBak (2012), Noori (2013) and Talebinejad and Nekouei (2013) conducted with different groups of people. The review of a sample of recently published studies in this respect shows that anxiety-related research has been in consonance with other mainstream studies in other EFL contexts across the globe.

Atef-Vahid and Kashani (2011) revealed that although some students felt extremely confident and relaxed, however, one-third of the students experienced moderate to high-anxiety levels while learning the English language in class. English classroom anxiety had the highest correlational value among other types of anxiety in FLCAS.

Yousefi, Azarfam and Baki (2012) mentioned that Language anxiety involves three connected anxieties: communication apprehension; test anxiety; and fear of negative evaluation. It is clear that a foreign language class can be more anxiety-provoking than any other course for many students (Liu, 2007 ;Ohata , 2005).

Trang (2012) found out that traditionally, anxiety research has focused mainly on the state-trait anxiety in investigating the role of anxiety in language learning. According to such an approach, language anxiety is a transfer of other more general types of anxiety. Therefore, test-anxious students feel so because they felt that they are constantly tested. Also, shy people feel uncomfortable when asked to communicate publicly. Early studies adopting such approach yielded conflicting results about the effects of anxiety on achievement and performance. Serraj and Noordin (2013) revealed in their study that there was a negative correlation between FLLA and listening comprehension and a negative correlation between FLA and listening comprehension whereas FLA and FLLA enjoyed a positive correlation. It could be concluded that the relationship between Foreign Language Anxiety and Foreign Language Listening Anxiety of the participants were in accordance with each other. Furthermore the result showed that the impact of FLLA on Iranian students' listening comprehension skill was significantly more problematic.

Awan, et al. (2010) revealed that language anxiety and achievement are negatively related to each other. It is also found that female students are less anxious in learning English as a foreign language than male students. Speaking in front of others is rated as the biggest cause of anxiety followed by "worries about grammatical mistakes", pronunciation and "being unable to talk spontaneously".

Ay (2010) found out that the students' level of instruction was taken into account as the main source of anxiety.

In addition, Dordinejad and Ahmadabad (2014) foreign language classroom anxiety was found to be significantly and negatively correlated with English language achievement. Females were found to be more anxious than their male counterparts.

According to Ushida (2005) as cited by Nyamubi (2016), motivation mediates the relationship between language attitudes and language achievement. The current study, however, examined the role students' language attitudes in their performance in English without including motivation as mediating factor between the two variables under study, because other studies have dealt with this (Gardner, 2000, Ushida, 2005).

Al-Saraj (2011) explains why Saudi Arabian culture creates a social and cultural setting for examining FLA. The education system in Saudi Arabia is free for all levels, where male and female students are separated, typically attending segregated schools. The combination of factors such as the importance of learning English, the educational system and conservative culture create an environment for FLA. Moreover, the study where only females were participating showed, that giving live, in-class presentations causes strong anxiety for them.

In the research by Al-Saraj (2011), majority of the participants pointed out teachers characteristics as the major cause of their anxiety. Teachers no-sense explaining of the subject, over-correcting the students and visible favoritism strongly contributed to increasing anxiety by the students as well. Moreover, teachers authoritative nature, embarrassing and humiliating attitude towards students create stressful environment in the class (Tanveer, 2007). Therefore, it is important that teachers pay attention to signals of anxiety radiating from the students and accommodate the later steps.

AlAsmari (2015) found out that participants have not exhibited any significant differences in the perceptions of Saudi preparatory year students regarding FL anxiety in relation to their English language proficiency. At the elementary school level, Alshahrani & Alandal (2015) investigated the level of FLA and the impact of gender differences among 146 male and 114 female 6th grade Saudi students. The results showed that FLA was moderate and gender difference did not play a significant impact on anxiety towards foreign language learning. Alrabai, (2014) also conducted a study to investigate the levels and sources of foreign language anxiety (FLA) among 1389 Saudi (male and female) EFL learners. The participants were of intermediate, high and university levels. The participating learners reported moderate to high levels of anxiety, with communication being the key cause of learners' language anxiety.

Javid (2014) revealed that Saudi preparatory year bear medium level of language learning anxiety. Among the four anxiety factors, communication apprehension anxiety remained at the top followed by English classroom anxiety. Fear of negative evaluation anxiety has been assigned the third position and test anxiety got the least average mean.

Furthermore, Al-Saraj (2014) examined the anxiety level of 83 EFL female students – in a College Preparatory Program (CPP)- using the Arabic Foreign Language Anxiety Questionnaire (AFLAQ). The study revealed that participants' average AFLAQ scores ranged from 1.80 to 4.30 out of 5.00; the mean score across participants in Level 1 was 3.33, Level 3 was 3.25 and Level 4 was 2.95.

Ezzi (2012) conducted a study in Yemen in Hodeidah University. The number of the participants is 163 students enrolled in the third and the fourth year. The data was collected using Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale and the result shows that female students experience higher level of anxiety than male students.

Awan and her colleagues (2010) employed FLCAS to examine FLL anxiety among 149 undergraduate learners with regard to the type of situations that provoke anxiety during different stages of the learning process and the relationship of anxiety with learners' achievement. It was found that female students are less anxious in learning English as a foreign language than male students. Communication anxiety and English classroom environment were rated as the biggest causes of anxiety among Pakistani EFL learners, respectively.

Another study is conducted by Kamarulzaman et al. (2013) investigated the difference in the level of anxiety between males and females. The result revealed that females experience higher level of anxiety than males.

Arnaiz and Guillén's (2012) investigated that foreign language anxiety regarding individual differences indicated that participants showed an average level of anxiety in which females were more anxious than males; and that lower level students proved to be more anxious.

Cheragian et al. (2008) found out that most of the students had low and moderate levels of anxiety. Also, they found no significant relationship between test anxiety and the students' total average score; however, high anxiety led to an increase in the students' poor performance. The researchers suggested that in addition to special attention to this problem, more studies should be conducted to identify the related causes and provide strategies for decreasing anxiety among students (ibid).

Nakhaei, et al. (2010) showed on their study that the group based on overall consciousness in experimental group had less anxiety in the examinations compared with the group based on study skills in control group.

Rukh (2014) concluded in his study that students have positive attitudes towards learning English in association with achievement. In another study Al samadeni and Ibnian (2015) found that "students with high GPAs have the highest positive attitudes towards learning English, followed by the medium GPA students and finally the low GPA students".

Hussain, Shahid and Zaman, (2011), found a negative correlation between foreign language anxiety and students' attitude towards English. Female students had a positive attitude toward English and less anxiety. Also, rural students were found to have a higher anxiety level and low attitude towards English. Similarly, Liu and Chen (2013), in their study, found that students who had a higher level of positive attitudes had significantly lower anxiety.

Local

In a recently published study, Mamhot, Martin and Masagya (2013) examined language learning anxiety among 40 EFL respondents in the Philippines administering FLCAS and complementary questionnaires. The general results of this study showed that the Filipino learners had a high level of fear of negative evaluation regarding low self-perceived linguistic competency.

Rochele Irene Lucas, et al. (2011) conducted a study at De La Salle University - Manila, showed that English Language learners would equip themselves with learning strategies that would help them not only to learn the target but also to cope with their language learning anxieties. It was also found that test anxiety is and fear of negative evaluation constitutes the type of learning anxieties these were students experiencing. It can be gleaned from the results that foreign learners experience anxiety if they are being evaluated by both their peers and their teachers as to their performance in using the target language. This is rooted perhaps because of negative affective experience when they were learning the language and also, they would like to avoid 'losing face' in their English Language class.

Furthermore, it has been proved that reading anxiety exists, especially that there will always be the

involvement of a learner's affective domain even in academic setting where cognitive faculties are much more needed. In fact, the study affirms that reading anxiety comes in three different categories, namely top-down reading, bottom-up reading, and classroom reading. In the case of MSU ILS Grade 8 students, it is at a high level. It sends a message that anxiety greatly takes place while students undergo the process of reading a text written in English (Guima & Alico, 2015).

Gomari and Lucas (2013) had a study which was conducted in Manila, the capital city of the Philippines, and the subjects were selected from four different private universities in Metro Manila. The results of the FLCAS survey showed that Iranian EFL learners in the Philippines generally experience anxiety while learning the English language. The primary source of anxiety for Iranian EFL learners in this study was Test Anxiety. This was followed, respectively, by Communication Apprehension, English Classroom Anxiety, and Fear of Negative Evaluation.

Awan et al. (2010) investigated the relationship between foreign language classroom anxiety and the students' achievement using a short form of FLCAS and an inventory of situations that causes anxiety. They reported a negative relationship between language anxiety and achievement. They also found that females are less anxious than males in learning English and the main cause of anxiety was speaking in front of other students in class.

The study of Del Villar (2010) sought to identify how beginning Filipino students explained their fears about oral communication. Only by knowing his/her students' fear would a teacher be able to tailor the most suitable teaching-learning activities. Results revealed an 8 factor model explaining 69.11% of the total variance in the data. The factors were: expectation, training and experience, audience, self-worth, rejection, verbal fluency, preparation and previous unpleasant experience. These factors were the attributions for the fears beginning Filipino students with them when they first stepped into the communication 3 classrooms.

In the study conducted by Capulet, et al. (2013) on the Language Anxiety and Academic Self-concept was primarily to determine if language anxiety has a significant relationship on the students' level of

academic self-concept particularly among Bachelors of Arts in English Sophomore of the University of Southeastern Philippines, Inigo St; Bo. Obrero, Davo City, school year 2008-2009. The study involved thirty Bachelor of Arts in English Sophomore of the University of Southeastern Philippines during the second semester of school 2008-2009.

Results of the study showed that the level of language anxiety of the Bachelor of Arts in English Sophomore is $y=2.98$. This means that the level of language anxiety the students is average. Furthermore, the result of the study showed that the level of language anxiety of the Bachelor of Arts in English Sophomore of the University of Southeastern Philippines - Obrero, for the school year 2008-2009, has no significant correlation on their Academic Self-Concept and any of its four facets.

Synthesis

The aforementioned literature and studies have a positive influence in this study because of the relevant insights on investigating the impact of students' attitude towards English language on academic achievement. The researcher claimed that the language anxiety of the students can be attributed to many factors but mostly, based from the study, it can be inferred that productivity of students is hampered in terms of their performance in English because of the many factors surrounding the language; this includes: being fearful of making mistakes, gaining criticism as a result of the mistakes, their limited capacity to express themselves, and their insufficiency in terms of the knowledge on the subject content.

This study claimed that students faced factors that impede performance in the classroom. These experiences are oftentimes contributing to their anxiety in the class. Moreover to address the issues on students' attitude and anxiety faced by the junior high students when using English as a medium of expression in class interaction. Speaking activities to diminish if not eradicate anxiety will be proposed to make the teaching and learning process meaningful and productive especially in learning the English language.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the research method used in this study. This describes the research locale, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering

procedure and the statistical tools used in analyzing the data.

Research Design

The descriptive quantitative method of research was used to determine the impact of English language anxiety on the students' academic achievement. To measure the anxiety level of English language classroom activity anxiety and the attitude of grade 9 students toward English a Likert-scale was used and rated with the following options: Strongly Disagree - 1, Disagree - 2, Undecided - 3, Agree - 4, Strongly Agree - 5, 1 - Very Relaxed, 2 - Moderately Relaxed, 3 - Anxious, 4 - Moderately Anxious, 5 - Very Anxious.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Felisberto Verano National High School located at Poblacion, Cortes, Surigao del Sur of Caraga (Region XIII). The school situated in a hilly portion of the barangay, is the former building of the Municipality of Cortes.

This school is the central school in the Municipality of Cortes; it offers Junior high school Grades 7 to 10, General Academics (GAS), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Technical Vocational Livelihood, specifically cookery for the grade 11 Senior High School Students. There are 16 teaching personnel and 5 non-teaching personnel of the school with 545 students enrolled in the current school year. Figure 2 presents the geographical location of Felisberto Verano National in the District of Cortes, Division of Surigao del Sur.

Figure2. Map of the Research Locale

Respondents of the Study

This study used universal sampling because it considered the two classes of the grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School. One class was composed of 43 learners and the other class was comprised of 45 students with a total of 88 students as the chosen respondents of this study.

The researcher chose to work with the grade 9 students who are grouped heterogeneously. The researcher generally observed that most of the students, but not all showed less importance in English as an academic subject; in fact, only a few of them participated in class discussion especially when asked to give insights about the topic. However, when it comes to group activities such as role playing they had showcased their skills with extra ordinary talent. Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents

	Total Population	Sample Respondents
Class A	43	43
Class B	45	45
Total	88	88

Research Instrument

In this study, the participants were asked to complete a survey questionnaire on the Attitude Towards English (Appendix C) and the level of anxiety towards English Language Activity (Appendix D). The first instrument used was a 10 – item standardized questionnaire of Alessia Occhipinti (2009) that used a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 1- strongly disagree, 2- disagree, 3 - undecided, 4 - agree to 5- strongly agree.

The second instrument has 25-item questions using a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 1- very relaxed, 2- moderately relaxed, 3 - anxious, 4 - moderately anxious to 5- very anxious. This English version of foreign language classroom attitude scale checklist is standardized based on Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) as cited by Vahid (2011).

These instruments were designed to gather data from the respondents in order to analyse students' response, to have a deep view and to draw their perception on

the impact of students' attitude towards english language on academic achievement.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to gathering the data, the researcher sent a letter of intent to the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct this study. With the Superintendent's endorsement, the researcher gave a copy of the said letter to the School Principal of Felisberto Verano National High School; thus, the researcher was able to administer the test to the student-respondents.

Before distributing the questionnaires, the researcher explained the purpose and the importance of this study and the ways on how to fill out the questionnaires. The conduct of the study was done during the usual teaching hours. The questionnaires were administered to the grade 9 Junior High School Students. Administration of the questionnaire to the students was done within a 30-minute period during the second week of December 2017.

After administering the test, the questionnaires were retrieved personally by the researcher to ensure the hundred percent retrieval. Data were then tallied tabulated, analyzed, treated, and interpreted. After the interpretation of the data, inferences, conclusions were derived and recommendations were offered.

Statistical Treatment

The statistical tools used in analyzing the data of this study were weighted mean and Pearson Product Moment of Correlation (Pearson-r). The weighted mean was used to determine the attitude of Grade 9 students towards English language class and the level of anxiety towards English during class activities using the MPS for the second grading of A.Y. 2017-2018 as data.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson-r) was used to determine the significant relationships between the respondent's MPS and Attitude towards English Language, MPS and Level of Anxiety towards English Class Activities and finally, the significant relationship between attitude and the level of anxiety.

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the data gathered which were analysed and interpreted following the sequence of the statement of the problem.

Attitude of Grade 9 Students towards English Language Class Activities

Table 2 shows the mean results of the tallied Attitude of Grade 9 students towards English language class activities.

Table 2 Attitude of Grade 9 Students towards English Language Class Activities

Attitudes	Mean	Adjectival Rating
1	2.26	Agree
2	2.88	Agree
3	2.12	Slightly Disagree
4	3.11	Agree
5	2.78	Agree
6	2.96	Agree
7	2.12	Slightly Disagree
8	2.44	Slightly Disagree
9	2.57	Slightly Disagree
10	2.82	Agree
Over-all Mean	2.61	Agree

As the table revealed, the grade 9 students exhibited a negative attitude towards English as a subject. From the benchmark statements, it was underscored that they do not like English. This suggests that students generally dislike English as a subject because they find it difficult to express themselves using the language as a medium for communication. Furthermore, English as a subject is rule-governed and these students are not familiar with the rules of grammar which make it difficult for them to construct correct sentences. This is in consonance with the statement of Al Samadeni and Ibnian (2015) when they articulated that students with high GPAs have the highest positive attitude towards learning English, followed by the medium GPA students and finally the low GPA students. This means that as the GPA declines, attitude towards English also shifts from positive to negative.

Statement with the lowest mean is on “I have heard of the phrase Filipino-English” with 2.12 and adjectival rating of slightly disagree. This means that students are unaware of Filipino English when they hear of the word “English,” they do not have an idea as to the variants of English revealing the limited knowledge they have on the said language.

Level of English Language Anxiety

Table 3 shows the results of the level of english language anxiety.

Table 3 Level of English Language Anxiety

Indicators	Mean	Adjectival Rating
1	2.26	Anxious
2	2.57	Anxious
3	2.85	Anxious
4	2.38	Moderately Relaxed
5	2.78	Anxious
6	2.82	Anxious
7	2.80	Anxious
8	2.59	Moderately Relaxed
9	2.18	Moderately Relaxed
10	2.52	Moderately Relaxed
11	2.79	Anxious
12	2.67	Anxious
13	2.72	Anxious
14	2.52	Moderately Relaxed
15	2.90	Anxious
16	2.89	Anxious
17	2.43	Moderately Relaxed
18	2.90	Anxious
19	2.35	Moderately Relaxed
20	2.39	Moderately Relaxed
21	2.78	Anxious
22	2.76	Anxious
23	2.73	Anxious
24	2.79	Anxious
25	2.84	Anxious
Over- all Mean	2.65	Anxious

When a teacher conducts a speaking activity such as debate, students display anxiety. The anxiety can be attributed to the fear that debate activity requires students to speak spontaneously about their stand on a certain issue of which students find this situation to be upsetting, thus nervousness sets in. Furthermore, students are also anxious when the teacher does not clarify to everyone that everyone is culpable of making mistakes, thus because they do not want to be laughed at that they are afraid when asked to speak in front of everyone. The statement that gained a mean rating of 2.18 with the adjectival rating of moderately relaxed is on the item wherein students do not feel nervous even when they are asked to speak in front when they are not corrected by their teacher or classmates. This implies that corrections make them upset since students have not developed the value of appreciation for positive criticism.

Many researchers have pointed out that the skill producing most anxiety is speaking according to MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) in Go, et al. (2011);

this anxiety comes in part from a lack of confidence in the learners' general linguistic knowledge but if only this factor were involved; all skills would be affected equally. Moreover, Young (1991) in Go, et al. (2011) compiled a list of classroom activities which are perceived by students as anxiety-producing activities: (1) spontaneous role play in front of the class; (2) speaking in front of the class; (3) oral presentations or skits performed in the class; (4) presenting a prepared dialogue in front of the class; and (5) writing work on the board. Error correction also turned out to play an important role in contributing to a students' anxiety. Furthermore, Palacios (1998) in Go, et al. (2011) also found the following classroom tasks characteristics to be anxiety-producing: demands of oral production, feeling of being put on the spot, the pace of the class, and the element of being evaluated.

Although many learners feel that some error correction is necessary Koch & Terrell (1991) and Horwitz (1988) explained that the manner of error correction is often cited as provoking anxiety. It has also been found that students are more concerned about how (i.e., when, what, where or how often, etc.) their mistakes are corrected than whether error correction should be administered in class. In relation to the fear of negative evaluation from others. Ohata (2005) in by Go, et al. (2011) also suggests that fear of losing "face" in front of others was also found to be a shared anxious feeling by language learners. These students have expressed anxiety in evaluative situations in which their knowledge and performance of English were to be monitored by people around them. This fear of losing "face" may be particularly

true for foreign students who may have the feeling of being under critical evaluation as far as their utterances, grammar use and other communication means are concerned.

MPS of the Respondents in the Second Grading Period

The Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School gained an MPS of Seventy Five (75) during the Second Grading Period of School year 2017-2018. This implies that these Junior High School students have reached only a passing rate in terms of their academic performance in English. This further connotes that students have difficulty in English. In the research locale as observed by the English teachers and other teachers teaching subjects taught in English, they observed that students have insufficient knowledge on vocabulary and English structure, and they lack the confidence to talk before a crowd. The study of Adelson, et al., (2014) underscored that students find difficulty in learning English as a second language because their knowledge of the English such as sentence structure, vocabulary, grammar, morphology and pragmatics is underdeveloped. Furthermore, they also posited that students' academic performance is largely affected with their processing, sequencing and memory problems, together with the difficulty in drawing inferences.

Significant Relationship between Respondents' MPS and Attitude Towards English

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and attitude towards English.

Table 4 Significant Relationship between Respondents' MPS and Attitude towards English

Variables Tested	Computed r	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Respondents' MPS and Attitude	0.357	0.001	Reject Null Hypothesis	Highly Significant

Table 4 shows the P-value of 0.001 rejecting the null hypothesis. This posits that there is a high significant relationship between the respondents MPS with their attitude towards English. Results imply that the way that students think and behave towards English language whether positive or negative is highly correlated to their academic performance. When students display a positive behavior towards the subject, most likely, they also perform academically well. However, when they manifest negative behavior towards the subject, academic performance is also affected because they are not interested to accomplish things related to the subject. This is supported by

Rukh (2014) when he concluded in his study that students have positive attitudes towards learning English in association with achievement. In another study Al samadeni and Ibnian (2015) found that students with high GPAs have the highest positive attitudes towards learning English, followed by the medium GPA students and finally the low GPA students."

Significant Relationship between the Respondents' MPS and Level of Attitude

Table 5 presents significant relationship between respondents' MPS and level of anxiety.

Table 5 Significant Relationship between the Respondents' MPS and Level of Attitude

Variables Tested	Computed r	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Respondents' MPS and level of Anxiety	0.113	0.310	Failed to reject Null Hypothesis	Not Significant

On the significant relationship between respondents' MPS and their level of attitude, the P-value 0.310 failed to reject the null hypothesis; therefore there is no significant relationship between attitude level on their academic performance. Result implies that whether the attitude level is high or low, the academic performance of the respondents is not affected, thus the increase or decrease on the academic performance is attributed to other factors not identified in this study. Also, the data reveals that students do not display attitude in the subject as a whole but during those moments when they are asked to speak in front of other people.

One of the studies is the one conducted by Awan et al. (2010) who investigated foreign language classroom anxiety in its relationship with students' achievement. It is revealed that language anxiety and achievement are negatively related to each other. It is also found that female students are less anxious in learning English as a foreign language than male students. Speaking in front of others is rated as the biggest cause of anxiety followed by "worries about

grammatical mistakes," pronunciation and "being unable to talk spontaneously."

Significant Relationship between Students' Attitude and the Level of Anxiety

Table 6 presents the significant relationship between students' attitude and the level of anxiety. On the significant relationship between students' attitude and the level of anxiety, the P-value is 0.800 failed to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no significant relationship between students' attitude and the level of anxiety. This implies that how students feel or behave towards English language does not necessarily have anything to do with their level of anxiety. The anxiety level of students could probably be affected by factors not identified in this study. Students' behavior towards English may sometimes be positive or negative, but the subject as a whole does not upset them or makes them anxious. In other words, when there are activities not exposing them to public eye, like writing and reading journals, they do not display antagonism to the subject. An activity that requires them to perform in front of other people triggers their anxiety but not at all times.

Table 6 Significant Relationship between Students' Attitude and the Level of Anxiety

Variables Tested	Computed r	P-value	Decision	Conclusion
Respondents' attitude and level of Anxiety	0.028	0.800	Failed to Reject Null Hypothesis	Not Significant

In the study conducted by Hussain, et al. (2011), they found out a negative correlation between foreign language anxiety and students' attitude towards English. Female students had a positive attitude toward English and less anxiety. Also, rural students were found to have a higher anxiety level and low attitude towards English. Similarly, Liu and Chen (2013). In their study, it was found out that students who had a higher level of positive attitudes had significantly lower anxiety.

Suggested Speaking Activities

Rationale

The students' attitude towards English language level of the Grade 9 students of Felisberto Verano National High School, Cortes I District was investigated

through their levels of anxiety based on the Mean Percentage Score. The study indicates that majority of the students are anxious towards the English subject and results to anxiously speaking in the said subject.

Teachers all over the Philippines are asking students to create and deliver speeches as part of their collection of evidence showing progress toward state standards. However, many educators do not have a background in speaking instruction or do not feel confident in helping students meet this standard. Moreover, speaking activities have been developed to provide teaching strategies for public speaking and to share a collection of quality classroom speaking activities.

Objectives:

- Develop fundamental listening and speaking skills;
- Learn and apply knowledge of adjective vocabulary to describe various objects;
- Practice speaking and listening to the present perfect tense and the differences between for and since;
- Ask and answer questions in front of the class;
- Review vocabulary and practice communication;
- Review previous information, to gather information from a partner through interviewing, and discuss opinions with a partner;
- Practice explaining cultural icons to English speaking foreigners;

questions left, points can also be increased to enhance the competition. The group who will earn the most points at the end of the game will be declared as winners.

Materials and Preparation:

WHO/WHAT AM I? A WARM UP ACTIVITY

Prepare a list of 10 questions with 3 hints each as well as an extra hint for each question (in case students cannot guess by the third hint). Here is an example of a PERSON question: Lady Gaga. Hint No. 1: I am famous for my great fashion style and my beautiful voice. Hint No. 2: I am a female American pop singer. Hint No. 3: One of my famous songs is 'Just dance'. Extra Hint (Hint No. 4): The first part of my name is 'Lady.'

Target Group: All Grades

Difficulty Level:
Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:
To develop fundamental listening and speaking skills

Students' Task:
Students will be placed in groups with 4-5 members. Groups will be numbered from 1 onwards and a scoreboard will be written up. Students must listen carefully to 3 hints and try to guess the thing or person as quickly as possible by raising their hands. Alternatively, each group will be given a chance to answer and if they cannot answer correctly, the next group can try to answer and so on. Each hint is worth points: i.e. If students can guess by Hint No. 1 they will receive 30 points; Hint No. 2 is worth 20 points and Hint No. 3 is worth 10 points. If a 4th hint is needed, this will be worth 5 points. The focus will be on 10 questions about things (e.g. food, sports etc.) and/or people. This activity can also be used to review previously studied content. When there are only 2-3

Teacher's tasks:

PREPARATION: The teacher will create the questions that correspond to the academic level of the students.

BEFORE THE ACTIVITY: The teacher will divide the students into groups, numbers the groups, and puts up a scoreboard. Lastly, the teacher will use the example question in order to explain the game to the students.

DURING THE ACTIVITY: The teacher will give the hints, check to see which group had their hands raised first in order to answer the question. Furthermore, the teacher will keep a record of the scores and update the scoreboard as groups answer the questions correctly. When it has reached the last three questions, it is at the discretion of the teacher as to how many points the game will be increased by (as it all depends on the scores).

Suggestions and Advice:

1. When preparing the questions, always prepare an extra 2-3 questions in case you need a tie breaker.
2. Make sure the example question is easy for the

students to follow.

- The hints should neither be too easy nor too difficult; the first hint should never be too obvious.
- Instead of having students all raise their hands at once, have only one student from each group stand up for each round and guess on behalf of their group (it is easier to manage the game this way for rowdy classes).
- Constantly check the reaction of the students and use the blackboard to draw/ write clues if students do not understand the vocabulary being used in the hints.

NAME THAT ADJECTIVE

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level: Fundamentals

Activity Objective:

To learn and apply knowledge of adjective vocabulary to describe various objects

Students' Tasks

Students will be introduced to adjective vocabulary relating to touch, size, shape and color through the use of flashcards. After repeating the vocabulary words, students will be given a hand-out with

an adjective word bank and table containing a list of various objects. Students will form small groups of 4-5 students. Each group will receive different objects provided by the Teacher. The students will examine the object and write four adjectives to describe that object. The teacher will demonstrate an example for students. The objects will rotate through the small groups until each group has received all of the objects. Students will fill out the table by writing four

adjectives to describe each object. If groups finish early, students will write descriptive sentences using the information in the table. An example sentence will be provided on the hand-out for students.

Materials and Preparation:

Adjective flashcards about touch, size, shape and color will be used for introducing adjective vocabulary to students. The teacher will hold up various flashcards and have students say each word aloud. Students will fill in the table with four adjectives to describe each object. Various objects including a fake flower, stuff animal, magnet, bubble wrap, seashells, cloth and picture frame will be passed around to each small group. Students will describe each object after viewing and interacting with it.

Teacher's Tasks

- The teacher will take turns holding up the adjective flashcards. The teacher will say each word twice and have the students repeat the word after them. The teacher will pass out the hand-out to students.
- Teacher will explain the directions on how to complete the hand-out. The teacher will choose some students to repeat the directions to check for understanding. The teacher will demonstrate an example for the class using a toy train.
- Teacher will give one object to each group and walk around the classroom to provide assistance and feedback during the activity. The teacher will signal students when to change objects. At the end of the class, the teacher will collect the objects and hand-outs from students and end the class.

Suggestions and Advice:

To make this activity run more smoothly teachers can determine small groups ahead of time for effective student placement. The teacher should also establish rules for handling the objects at the beginning of the class, for example, treat the objects with care and do not throw objects across the room. A timer can be

used to determine how long each group will have each object. The teacher should determine and explain how the objects are to be rotated through the groups to avoid confusion among the students. During the activity, teachers should provide more support for students that are off task or struggling.

SOMETHING HAS BEEN STOLEN

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level:
Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:

To practice speaking and listening to the present perfect tense and the differences between for and since.

Teacher Tasks:

The teachers start this activity by announcing that something has been stolen and there are five thieves in the classroom. The students are now detectives and must interview other students to find the five thieves. Each student receives one card. This card has answers written in broken English for the students to build sentences on, for example, [be a member of soccer club] [2 years]. The example sentence would be "I have been a member of soccer club for 2 years." There are 6 of these answers. Students interview three fellow students and write down the answers in third person "He has played baseball since last year." After each student has interviewed three other students, the teachers read out the details of the thieves. After the details have been said, the teachers ask the students if they have found a thief. The "thieves" are brought to

the front of class and made to do an easy task (asking them questions to answer in the present perfect tense).

Materials and Preparation:

Present Perfect grammar lesson, 40 cards (5 of which match the details the teachers will give), interview sheets, and thieves sheet for the teachers to read out at the end).

Suggestions and Advice:

This activity has been one of my most successful activities. I find that stressing the roll-playing aspect of this activity (that they are detectives and that five of their fellow students are thieves) make this activity more enjoyable. During the thieves information part, I found that having all the students start with their hands raised and only lowering them when they have no matches works much better than giving the information and asking who the thieves are afterwards. Also, when making cards, make sure that most of the information matches up to the thieves' information until the last questions. This keeps the students very interested in listening because they think they have caught at least one thief until they hear the last question.

DO - IT - MYSELF QUIZ

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level:
Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:

To ask and answer questions in front of the class

Students' Tasks

1. Learn vocabulary of new lesson using flashcards and repetition, class chorus responses.
2. Show examples of Who/Which/Whose sentences using relative pronouns explaining how they are used in the sentence.

3. Instructions: Students will create 12 questions using relative pronouns on three given sheets. Ex. The river which is the longest in the world. Answer: The Nile. Sheet A includes questions about the new lesson (please use some new vocabulary words) and each question is worth 3 points. Sheet B includes questions about the 2 previous lessons and each question is worth 2 points. Sheet C includes questions about anything else (i.e. Japan, food, famous characters) and each question is worth 1 point. Students are divided into 4 groups of 5 students and are given 12 minutes to create questions and include answers.
4. Check questions and answers for validity and grammar, receive team points for creating questions.
5. Each team selects 6 questions to ask in front of the class. Reading them aloud and choosing the team to answer. For each correct answer, the answering team and the team posing the question receives team points based on which Sheet (A, B or C) is used.
6. Give each team points for questions and answers.
7. Determine a winner, receive prize!

Moreover, the teacher can help too, walking around the classroom.

4. Language teacher collects sheets and gives team points for correctly composed sentences with answers and records score on the board.
5. Language teacher encourages students as they ask questions to the class, maybe helping with pronunciation, calling on teams to answer and recording teams' scores on the board and calls up next group.
6. Awards prizes to students participation.

Suggestions and Advice:

During #3, having the Language teacher walks around the room and helping students start relative pronoun sentences really helps. Getting the students started on a sentence and giving ideas for topics or helping them correct sentences will help students to create a non-pressured situation for the students to ask questions. This also creates a sense of comfort to ask questions about instructions or content during the class period.

ARTICULATE

Materials and Preparation:

Prepare flashcards, Sheets A, B and C; one for each group. Team flags for answering questions and group names and have prizes for winning team.

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level:

Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:

To review vocabulary and practice communication

Teacher's tasks:

1. Language teacher prepares flashcards including new English words with accent and using flashcards during the lesson to respond with the class.
2. Language teacher prepares examples of relative pronoun sentences, writes on the board, and explains how the relative pronoun works within the sentence.
3. Language teacher gives instructions (using gestures of course) and checks the sentences that student groups create, correcting if necessary.

Students' Task:

1. Students make pairs and one student "goes to sleep" (puts their head on the desk so they can't see what will be written on the blackboard). The teacher writes a word on the board (recently learnt vocabulary, key word for the lesson, etc.) which only the "awake" students read and rubs the word off the board and all students "wake up."
2. The students who read the word have to describe it to their partner in English (no actions, no spelling clues, no "sounds like"). Repeat as many times as desired with students switching roles.

Materials and Preparation:

No materials required. The words to be used simply need to be decided beforehand. Recently learnt vocabulary and key words for the lesson are recommended.

Teacher’s tasks:

The teacher supervises the activity, ensuring students obey the rules and use correct English. If students get stuck they can ask either teacher for help.

Suggestions and Advice:

This is a fun activity which can be used as a warm up; it can also be made into a more competitive game by adding a time limit for each round and introducing prizes or forfeits for the fastest and slowest pairs.

PETS ARE PEOPLE TOO!

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level: Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:

To review previous information, to gather information from a partner through interviewing, and to discuss opinions with a partner

Students’ Tasks:

Exercise 1 (review): students listen to a short passage and then answer T/F questions about it. Exercise 2

(interview): students first write their own answers and then ask partner and take note of partner's answers. Change partner when I say "go" and repeat process.

Exercise 3 (discussion): students first write their answers and then share their opinion with their partner and discuss the answers.

Materials and Preparation:

Materials: Hand-out

Teacher’s tasks:

Teacher: explains activities and call on students to answer. Shout out "go" to cue students to change seats. Teacher: walks around and help students as needed.

Suggestions and Advice:

A 50 minute class may not be enough time to thoroughly finish all exercises. Some of the pair discussions may be assigned as homework and discussed during the following class.

ORDERING FOOD

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level:
Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:

The ultimate goal of this lesson is to enable students

to order food in English in a familiar setting.

Teacher's Tasks

1. The teacher will be responsible for preparing the worksheets, creating the menu, eliciting answers from each group and ask the students (or each other) questions about the foods. E.g. Have you eaten this before? Begin with a warm up activity: Divide students into groups of 4-5 students. Give students 1 minute to write down as many English food names as possible. Ask groups to read out their list to the class, and write the food names on the board. The group with the most items wins. Next, explain to the students that we will be practicing how to order food from a menu. Give each student a menu, and a script sheet. Explain unfamiliar items on the menu. Give a demonstration role play using the worksheets.
2. The teacher will be the waiter, while the other students will be the customer. As the conversation progresses, the waiter chooses several items off the menu and will take notes, writing down what was ordered and its price. At the end, the teacher will repeat everything that was ordered and tell the other students how much the final cost is. Now it is the students turn to practice in pairs. Once students have finished, they can change pairs. Once the students have completed the exercise a few times, they can try it without taking notes.

Materials and Preparation:

1 Lined and numbered worksheet per group for the warm up activity. Students will use this to write down food names in English. 1 Practice script and 1 Menu for each student. Students will use these to practice ordering food in their pairs. Whiteboard or Blackboard for writing answers from the warm up.

Suggestions and Advice:

This activity will run more smoothly if the teacher has prepared questions about the categories to be included in the activity. For example, "Have you tried (food name) before?" or "Do you like (food name) ?"

Ideally, the menu would be something that the students are familiar with, but is from the teacher's home country (as in the example, New Zealand McDonalds Menu). If it is a low level class, it'd be a good idea to get the students to practice repeating the conversation after the teachers, before working in pairs.

ABOUT MY CULTURE

Target Group: All grades

Difficulty Level:
Basic Conversation

Activity Objective:
To practice explaining cultural icons to English speaking foreigners

Teacher's Tasks

This activity is to teach students how to explain the significance of items that are special to Philippine culture. After learning relevant vocabulary (e.g. culture, custom, luck, tradition, etc.), the class will brainstorm items/professions/people/etc that are important to Philippine culture (e.g. rice, tourists spots, etc.) and write them on the chalkboard. Then groups of 3-4 students will choose 5 items and write them on their paper. For each item, the group will write one sentence describing why the item is important (Ex: Rice is important in Philippines because we eat it every day.) The group will then choose one item and expand the explanation to several sentences. Finally, the group will present their object (or a picture of their object) to the class and explains why it is important to Filipino culture.

The Teacher will be responsible for preparing the materials, directing the activity, writing examples and brainstormed items on the chalkboard, showing examples, and facilitating English conversation in the classroom. He/she would assist in teaching the activity and making sure the students understood what

would be required of them, helping with translations (when necessary), and assisting students with the activity.

Materials and Preparation:

Worksheet with directions, example, and place to write sentences (Teacher prepares before class and prints enough for each student to have one.) English/Filipino dictionaries (to help students look up unfamiliar vocabulary) Realia (examples of objects that the students can describe, if needed).

Suggestions and Advice:

First, know your students' English level. If the level of English of your students is low, you can consider this lesson with your Grade 9 students, but I believe that this could be done at any level if modified. If students are struggling, more examples might help. Sentence patterns are very helpful here. If students have a known grammatical pattern to follow, they are more comfortable with the activity.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations of the study.

Findings

Based on the data gathered the following findings were drawn:

The findings revealed that the grade 9 students who participated in this study generally have negative attitude towards English as a subject, which obtained the highest rank 3.11. The results revealed that they disliked English as a subject because they find it difficult to express themselves using the language as a medium for communication. Moreover, on the statement "I have heard of the phrase Filipino-English" got the lowest rank 2.12 which means they were unaware or they do not have an idea of Filipino-English phrase.

As to their level of anxiety, it was also revealed in the study that most of the students have difficulty when the teacher gives a speaking activity requiring mental adeptness such as debate. Moreover, they also display hesitation when speaking before a crowd because of their fear of being corrected in front of everybody as revealed by the respondents.

The Grade 9 students MPS for the Second Grading Period for School Year 2017-2019 reached only a rating of 75%.

On the significant relationship between the respondents' MPS and the attitude towards English, the way that students think and behave towards English language whether positive or negative is highly correlated to their academic performance. On the significant relationship between respondents MPS and level of anxiety, the P-value of 0.310 failed to reject the null hypothesis; therefore there is no significant relationship between anxiety level on their academic performance. On the significant relationship between students' attitude and level of anxiety, the P-value of 0.800 failed to reject the null hypothesis.

Based on the findings of the study, there is a need to come up with speaking strategies to provide an avenue where students can be most apprehensive. However, because the macro skills are complementary, other skills also need to be addressed.

Conclusion

On the basis of the aforementioned findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

The findings revealed that students performed averagely in terms of their academic performance in English; however, they are most challenged when asked to do speaking-related activities most especially those that require them to showcase sharp wittedness because of their lack of interest in English as an academic subject. It can be inferred that the student-respondents lack language proficiency necessary to understand the subject content. When students have learning barriers, these impede academic success. The learning barrier may also have something to do with their deficiency on the language rules needed in order for them to understand the subject. Likewise, it can be inferred from the study that students who were more anxious are less willing to participate in learning activities.

The language anxiety of the students can be attributed to many factors but mostly, based from the study, it can be inferred that productivity of students is hampered in terms of their performance in English because of the many factors surrounding the language which includes: being fearful of making mistakes, gaining criticism as a result of the mistakes, their limited capacity to express themselves, and their insufficiency in terms of the knowledge on the subject content.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following are recommended:

Students are encouraged to manage their negative thoughts toward English as an academic subject. Many of the anxious students essentially aggravate their anxiety by setting up unreasonable standards for their performance. Thus, students are advised to focus on opportunities that would benefit them in language learning.

Teachers also play a crucial role. They are suggested to acknowledge the students anxious feelings and help them realize their potentials for success. Further, in coming up with the lesson preparation and in identifying the classroom activities, teachers may involve them by suggesting activities which are not anxiety provoking. For those activities which may intensify anxiety, the teacher may also modify it by making innovative changes so that students will be less embarrassed during classroom performance. The giving of positive reinforcement may also be helpful in increasing the confidence of the students; thus, the teachers can practice this by incorporating creative reinforcements so that students will feel less anxious during class activities.

Teachers are also recommended to undertake the role of the researcher in their classroom before they employ strategies to help their students overcome anxiety, foster motivation and increase performance in the classroom.

School administrators are also encouraged to foster the teacher as a researcher approach among teachers as an invaluable tool to solve classroom related issues such as anxiety faced by the students on certain learning areas. This approach can bring about together theory and practice by integrating classroom-based knowledge and principle-based concepts to gain

positive effects on students' performance with respect to their academic engagements.

It is suggested that the intervention strategies proposed in this study be utilized by the language teachers to minimize if not eradicate problems of anxiety in the classroom.

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APPENDIX C**Attitude of High School Students of Felisberto Verano National High School towards English**

Dear Respondents. This questionnaire is prepared to collect data for a research and will take approximately 15 minutes to finish. This part is concerned with your attitude towards English language and the other part is concerned with your reactions in English class activities. Please be assured that your identity is completely confidential.

The instrument used was the standardized questionnaire of Alessia Occhipinti (2009). The questionnaire has 10-item questions using a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 1- strongly agree, 2- disagree, 3 - undecided, 4 - agree to 5- strongly disagree.

Direction: In this section please read each of the following statements carefully; then check the box that best represents the level of your agreement to the statement.

Level of Agreement

1= strongly agree

2= agree

3= undecided

4= agree

5= strongly disagree

Students' Attitude Towards English Language	1	2	3	4	5
1. English is an International Language					
2. English is the language used most widely in the world					
3. Knowing English Is important in understanding people from the countries.					
4. I do not like learning English.					
5. The non-native English speakers can also speak Standard English.					
6. I have heard of the phrase "World Englishes."					
7. I have heard of the phrase "Filipino English"					
8. When I speak English, I want to sound like a English speaker.					
9. When I speak English, I want to be identified clearly as Filipino.					
10. I am not confident in speaking English because of my accent.					

APPENDIX D**Students Reactions to in-Class Activities**

The second questionnaire has 25-item questions using a 5- point Likert scale ranging from 1- very relaxed, 2- moderately relaxed, 3 - anxious, 4 - moderately anxious to 5- very anxious. This questionnaire checklist is standardized based on Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) as cited by Vahid (2011) The english version of Foreign language classroom attitude scale.

Direction: In this section please read each of the following statements carefully; then check the box that best represents the level of your agreement to the statement.

1=Very Relaxed

2= Moderately Relaxed

3= Anxious

4= Moderately Anxious

5= Very Anxious

Students Reactions to in-Class Reactions		1	2	3	4	5
1	I would feel more confident about speaking in class if we practiced more.					
2	I would feel less self-conscious about speaking in class in front of others if I knew them better.					
3	I feel very relaxed in class when I have studied a great deal the night before.					
4	I am less anxious in class when I am not the only person answering a question.					
5	I think I can speak the English language pretty well, but when I know I am being graded, I mess up					
6	I would be more willing to volunteer answers in class if I weren't so afraid of saying the wrong thing.					
7	I enjoy class when we work in pairs					
8	I feel more comfortable in class when I don't have to get in front of the class.					
9	I would enjoy class if we weren't corrected at all in class.					
10	I am more willing to speak in class when we discuss current events.					
11	I would get less upset about my class if we did not have to cover so much material in such a short period of time.					
12	I enjoy class when we do skits in class.					
13	I would feel better about speaking in class if the class were smaller.					
14	I feel comfortable in class when I come to class prepared.					
15	I am more willing to speak in class when we have a debate scheduled.					
16	I am less anxious in class when I am not the only person answering a question.					
17	I like going to class when we are going to role play situations.					
18	I would not be so self-conscious about speaking in class if it were commonly understood that everyone makes mistakes and it were not such a big deal to make a mistake.					
19	I prefer to be allowed to volunteer an answer instead of being called on to give an answer.					
20	I am more willing to participate in class when the topics we discuss are interesting.					
21	I would be less nervous about taking an oral test in the English class if I got more practice speaking in class.					
22	I enjoy writing my journal and reflection when I can work with another student.					
23	I would feel uncomfortable if the instructor never corrected our mistakes in class.					
24	I feel uneasy when my fellow students are asked to correct my mistakes in class.					
25	I feel confident when I write sentence essays and reflection papers					